

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS ON PERFORMANCE OF BIOMEDICAL ASH IN CONCRETE

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Abstract:

In the field of material science research, rapid technological innovation is ongoing. In an effort to increase concrete's strength and durability, numerous experiments have been conducted globally over the past forty years. Consisting of cement, aggregates, and water, concrete has evolved into an engineered custom material with efficient new ingredients to meet the demands of the growing construction industry. This development is the result of continuous research and experimentation. Combining medical waste from several sources, such as clinics, hospitals, and research facilities, into one that could potentially endanger human, plant, or animal life is known as biomedical waste. Because of its large production, it cannot be handled or disposed of without taking any extra safety measures. Biomedical waste is typically burned in incinerators to create Biomedical Waste Ash (BMWA). Bio-Medical Waste Ash (BMWA) is a toxic waste material that has the potential to cause significant harm to human and environmental health, including cancer, genetic risk, early mortality, and permanent sickness. The ecosystem and subterranean water are contaminated by the landfill disposal of this trash. BMWA may be effectively disposed of by using it as a building material, which can lower the amount of poisonous and dangerous elements. Because it could contain poisonous materials like heavy metals, it is regarded as hazardous or deadly waste. BMWA is usually disposed of in a landfill in order to prevent environmental spread. Yet, none of the landfills are completely impervious to leaks.

This Project presents the influence of incinerated biomedical waste ash as cement replacement on the strength and permeation properties of concrete. For this purpose, a control concrete mix was made and four concrete mixes were made with four different proportions of 0%, 5%, 10%, 15% and 20% by cement weight, designed for M30 grade by following the steps given in IS10262 as 1:1.39:2.64:0.45 there are 45 cubes of 15 cm * 15 cm *15 cm in size and 24 cylinders of 15 cm internal diameter and 30 cm height are casted in our investigation. The cement is partially replaced by BMWA at 5, 10, 15 and 20% the max compressive strength and the max split tensile strength were noticed at 5% of cement was replaced with BMWA. The variation of both compressive strength and tensile strength are presented in line charts.

Keywords: Biomedical Waste Ash (BMWA), compressive strength, split tensile strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

Biomedical waste, generated from medical sources and activities is a cause of concern for environmentalist. These wastes are generated in the process of diagnosis treatment and similar activities pertaining to human and animals. Also in the production or testing of biological instruments/components. Biological waste is broadly classified as biological and non biological wastes that may or may not be infectious. According to ministry of environment and forest about 4,05,702 kg biomedical waste generated everyday in India out of which around 72% is disposed off. However more than 28% is biomedical waste is left unattended. Most common process of disposal of biomedical waste is incineration in specifically made for biomedical waste. Ash obtained after incineration of biomedical waste are used as landfill. However these wastes can effectively been used in concrete making which will result in reduce the demand of land for disposal of biomedical waste ash on one hand and protection of environment by reducing the consumption and production of cement on other hand.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Aubert et al., (2004) studied the use of biomedical waste ash on the compressive strength and the durability of hardened concrete and suggest the use of waste in concrete constitutes a potential means of adding value. Al-Mutairi et al., (2004) compared the compressive strength of mixtures made with bottom and fly hospital ash in order to evaluate the effectiveness of reusing hospital incinerator ash. Results showed that when 5% micro silica and fly ash were incorporated, the compressive strength of cubes was further increased. (Genazzini et al., 2003) the chance of incorporating hospital waste ashes in Portland cement-based materials is presented here. Ash characterization was performed by chemical analysis, X-ray diffraction, radioactive material detection, and fineness and density tests. Al-Rawas et al., (2005) investigated the potential use of incinerator ash as a replacement for sand and cement in cement mortars. The cement, sand and water mixing proportions were 1:3:0.7 respectively. Results showed that incinerator ash caused a reduction in slump values when it was used as a replacement for sand while an opposite trend was observed when it was used as a replacement for cement. (Genazzini et al., 2005) The new cement–ash composite systems have been tested for future applications in building materials. The additions of hospital ash in cement matrices to be potentially used as construction elements.

This involved the assessment of the effect of the additions on the physico mechanical properties of the building materials. Anastasiadou et al., (2011) evaluated the mechanical properties of the medical waste incineration bottom ash using different amounts of ordinary Portland cement (OPC) as a binder. Result showed that strength decreased as the percentage of cement loading was reduced. Filipponi et al., (2003) prepared the different mixes by blending hospital waste incinerator bottom ash with ordinary Portland cement in different proportions and at different water dosages. Results at curing times longer than 28 days and for waste dosages higher than 50% suggested that bottom ash exhibited weak pozzolanic property. (Azni et al., 2005) In Germany 50% of the ash produced from incinerated waste is used for the manufacturing of sound insulation walls at National roads, as well as, sub layers on the streets. 60% of the bottom ash is used for the construction of asphalt and as a sub layer of roads in Netherlands. Anastasiadou et al., (2011) studied the cement based stabilization/solidification of fly and bottom ash generated from incinerated hospital waste to reduce the leachability of the heavy metals present in these materials.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the present investigation and experimental program was carried out to investigate the suitability of use of biomedical waste ash as partial replacement of cement in concrete and effect of replacement of cement of biomedical waste ash on workability of concrete in general and on compressive strength in particular. The properties of materials used in this investigation is discussed here in after:

3.1. Materials

3.1.1. Cement

Ordinary Portland cement is used throughout in the investigation. The following tests are given below.

Table 1- Properties of cement (Method of test refers to IS: 4032: 1985)

S.no	Particulars of test	Test results	Followed IS specification
1	Standard consistency	32%	IS:4031(4)
2	Fineness	5%	IS:4031(1)
3	Specific gravity	3.16	IS:4031(11)
4	Initial Setting time	85 min	IS:4031(5)
	Final Setting time	490 min	

3.1.2. Fine aggregate

According to zone II included in this analysis and the subsequent studies, has been used in compliance with IS: 2386-1968 part III as a fine aggregate. The specific gravity of fine aggregate was 2.46.

Table 2- Result of Sieve Analysis Test for Fine Aggregate (FA)

Fineness Modulus = $272/100 = 2.73$. Results of sieve analysis of fine aggregate is given in table 2.

S.no	Sieve size	Weight retained (gm)	% of Weight retained	Cumulative of % Weight retained	% of weight passing
1	4.75mm	15	1.5	1.5	98.5
2	2.36mm	25	2.5	4	96
3	1.18mm	145	14.5	18.5	81.5
4	600 μ	405	40.5	59	41
5	300 μ	310	31.0	90	10
6	150 μ	100	10	100	0

3.1.3. Coarse aggregate

In this current study, commonly accessible coarse aggregate with 20 mm maximum size has been used. The aggregates are washed away and allowed to dry on dry surfaces to extract debris and gravel. The specific gravity and fineness modulus of coarse aggregate is 7.685.

Table 3 - Result of Recorded sieve analysis test for 20 mm Nominal size coarse aggregate (20mm CA) Fineness Modulus = $7685/100 = 7.685$.

S.no	Sieve size	Weight retained (gm)	% weight retained	Cumulative %Weight retained	% of weight passing
1	20mm	1380	69	69	31
2	10mm	610	30.5	99.5	0.5
3	4.75mm	10	0.5	100	0
4	2.36mm	0	0	100	0
5	1.18mm	0	0	100	0
6	600 μ	0	0	100	0
7	300 μ	0	0	100	0
8	150 μ	0	0	100	0
Total				7685	

3.1.4. Biomedical waste ash

The BMWA is obtained from Maridi Eco Industries(Andhra)Pvt. Ltd Bheemunipatnam, Visakhapatnam in the present study. It is grey in colour, coarser than cement but lighter in weight than cement. specific gravity of BMWA is 2.62.

3.2. Mix proportions

Concrete mix proportions were designed as per IS 10262:2009 & IS 456:2000 code. The resulting concrete is proportioned for M30 grade as per nominal mix design. The cement is replaced by bio-medical waste ash (BMWA) in percentages i.e., 0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20% and these specimens were tested for compression, split tensile strengths. The variations of compressive strength, split tensile strength with bio-medical waste ash (BMWA) discussed in the result section. The table 4 show the concrete mix proportions were designed as per IS: 10262:2009 & IS 456:2000 code for M30.

Table 4 - mix proportion

Cement	F.A	C.A	Water
437.77	612.56	1157.49	197
1	1.39	2.64	0.45

2.3. Preparation and casting of test specimens

According to Indian Standard BIS 10262:2009, the concrete mix proportion was specified for the required strength. The quantity of materials to make the concrete mix is measured. Dried ingredients (Cement, BMWA, coarse aggregate, and fine aggregate) were mixed in a mixer. Then the water, was mixed to produce standardized concrete. The casting method was carried out directly after mixing and checking for fresh properties as per BIS: 1199–1959.

Table 5 - Mix proportion for BMWA mix

Mix	Cement (%)	BMWA (%)	Fine aggregate (%)	Coarse Aggregate (%)
Conventional mix	100	0	100	100
Mix1	95	5	100	100
Mix2	90	10	100	100
Mix3	85	15	100	100
Mix 4	80	20	100	100

The strength of concrete was measured in two ways. First was by casting a cube (150 mm x 150 mm x 150 mm) and testing the compressive strength. The second was casting a cylinder (100 mm x 300 mm) and measuring the split tensile strength. The samples were held for almost a day and subsequently maintained at a temperature of 27°+2 °C. They have been separated from the molds and then preserved to the testing requirements for ambient curing.

4. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

4.1. Fresh properties

Fresh properties of concrete are observed at the time of concreting. To measure the fresh properties of concrete workability tests are very important. If concrete is good in workability will shows better properties in its life time. Before pouring concrete into the molds we need to check the workability by slump cone method. The workability test for concrete is confirms to IS 1199 – 1959.

Fig 1 slump test

4.2. Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties of concrete are primarily concerned with determining its strength, which can be assessed through various tests including compressive strength, split tensile strength. To ensure that concrete specimens are properly tested, a schedule is maintained to determine the appropriate date and time for testing. Specimens are cast in accordance with standard procedures and tested immediately after removal from curing tanks or curing tubs, with surface water wiped off as per IS: 516-1959.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result of experimental program carried out to determine workability, compressive strength and split tensile strength are discussed here in after.

5.1. Workability

Workability is the property of fresh concrete which is indicated by the amount of useful internal work required to fully compact the concrete without bleeding or segregation in the finished product. Result of workability of referral as well as concrete by using biomedical waste ash as partial replacement of cement is given in table 6 and figure 1 for visual observation. It is evident from table that workability of concrete from table that workability of concrete decreased with increase in replacement level. This may be due to the reason that being lighter than cement. Biomedical waste ash occupies more volume than cement on equal weight basis resulting which more water is needed for lubrication thereby decrease in workability resulting.

Table 6 - Workability of Concrete at different replacement level of cement

% Replacement of biomedical waste ash	Water cement ratio(cement + biomedical waste ash) (mm)	Slump (mm)
0	0.45	100
5	0.45	100
10	0.45	80
15	0.45	60
20	0.45	40

5.2. Compressive strength

Compressive strength is the maximum compressive stress that, under a gradually applied load a given solid material can sustain without fracture. Compressive strength is calculated by dividing the maximum load by the cross sectional area of a specimen in a compression test. It is observed that the Compressive strength of concrete specimens at 7 days and 28 days are increased with replacement level up to 5%, it achieved maximum strength at 5% & shows nearly same strength upto 10% replacement of referral concrete.

Table 7 - Variation of Compressive Strength at 7 days, 14 days and 28 days with Replacement of bio-medical waste ash for M30 grade concrete.

% of BMWA	Number of Days	Compressive Strength
0	7	27.89 MPa
	14	29.66 MPa
	28	38.41 MPa
5	7	34.76 MPa
	14	38.82 MPa
	28	43.01 MPa
10	7	31.80 MPa
	14	34.24 MPa
	28	40.12 MPa
15	7	28.47 MPa
	14	29.16 MPa
	28	33.31 MPa
20	7	20.16 MPa
	14	22.39 MPa
	28	28.42 MPa

4.2 Showing variation of compressive strength graphs

5.3. Splitting tensile strength

A total of 24 cylindrical samples were prepared. The split tensile strength results obtained after the curing of 14 days and 28 days are shown in the table 8.

Table 8 - Variation of Split tensile strength at 14 days & 28 days with replacement of bio-medical waste ash (BMWA) for M30 grade concrete.

% of BMWA	Number of Days	Compressive Strength
5	14	5.91 MPa
	28	6.39 MPa
10	14	3.87 MPa
	28	4.98 MPa
15	14	3.73 MPa
	28	4.67 MPa
20	14	3.66 MPa
	28	4.38 MPa

Table 8 represent the split tensile strength for 14 days and 28 days mixes with replacement of cement with bio-medical waste ash (BMWA) values. The split tensile strength of the four sets is also decreased with the increase in percentage of bio-medical waste ash (BMWA).

4.3 Graphs showing variation of tensile strength

6. CONCLUSION

From the above study following conclusions are drawn :-

1. Workability of concrete made using biomedical waste ash is lower than that of conventional concrete..
2. The compression strength of 5% was 6.71% higher compared with 10% BMWA substitution to cement. Relatively to 10%, 15%, & 20%.
3. Based on the split strength results, it was found that the optimum level of substitution of BMWA in concrete was 5%&10%.
4. The split tensile strength of 5% was 22.07% higher compared with 10% BMWA substitution to cement. Relatively to 10%, 15%, & 20%.
5. Replacement of BMWA with cement is found to improve the strength of concrete. The optimal dosage of replacement is found to be 5%&10%. Utilization of BMWA will avoid the disposal problems and related environmental issues. Utilization of BMWA will reduce the hazardous toxic materials.

This research work opens up plenty of possibilities for utilizing harmful toxic Bio-Medical Waste Ash (BMWA) replacement in concrete, thereby addressing the environmental and disposal problems of BMWA. It can be used as a building material in the construction field for various applications.

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